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Research Article

Phytochemical Screening in *Coriander Sativum* and *Cuminum Cuminum* Seeds

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ABSTRACT

Coriander sativum and Cuminum cyminum are important ayurvedic drugs used in the culinary, they are well-known therapeutic herbs that have served long as herbal medicines, treating various disorders. Recently, demand for traditionally used natural products is increasing tremendously, mainly with the natural drug medicine formulation. Since ancient times, herbal drugs have been used as a source of medicine for primary treatment. The use of herbal drugs over antibiotics has proven to show less/no side effects for the usage over a longer period. Cuminum is used as a fundamental ingredient in all cuisines around the globe, prized for its distinctive flavour and aroma and loaded with rich essential oils and a wide range of bioactive compounds. The seeds of coriander and cumin are known for their aromatic sensory properties, apart from their renowned usage for therapeutic properties that are attributed to diverse phytochemical compositions like polyphenols, tannins, saponins, flavonoids and essential oils, that help contribute towards antioxidant, anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, and digestive properties, both the spices are used as a medicinal agent. The present study explores phytochemical constituents, like phenols, tannins, and saponins. Estimation of total phenolic content by gallic acid equivalent, and evaluation of phytochemical screening, showed the maximum amount in methanolic extract in coriander 105.5 mg/g and 124 mg/g in cumin. Estimation of proteins by the Falin Lawry method 8000µg/mL of protein in Coriander 12000 µg/mL of protein in Cumin. The gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). The results of preliminary phytochemical screening showed the presence of bioactive compounds, the GC-MS analysis revealed the presence of 14 compounds detected in coriander and cumin seeds respectively.

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INTRODUCTION

Coriander seeds (*Coriandrum sativum*) are a staple in various culinary traditions and have been recognized for their medicinal properties in traditional medicine (Fig.No. a &b). The findings indicate that coriander seeds are rich in beneficial compounds, supporting their use in both dietary and medicinal contexts. It is used as an integral component in culinary traditions across the globe, known for its distinctive aroma and flavour, with a rich history in traditional medicine, that has been utilized for health care for various disorders. It belongs to the Apiaceae family and is commonly called cilantro. *Coriandrum sativum*, (L.) is a hardy annual herb that belongs to the natural order Umbelliferae. The popular name is derived from the generic, which comes from the ancient Greek *Koris*. Coriander has been cultivated from ancient times in the native of Southern Europe and China. These leaves have a different taste from the seeds, with citrus overtones. In Indian and Central Asian recipes, coriander leaves are used in large quantities. The dry fruits are known as coriander seeds. The seeds have a lemony citrus flavour when crushed, due to terpenes linalool and pinene. The roasted coriander seeds are called as Dhaniya dal used as snacks. It is the main ingredient of the two south Indian dishes includes sambhar and rasam. In Russia and Central Europe, coriander seed is an occasional ingredient in rye bread. The seeds are used in brewing of beer, particularly in Belgian wheat beers. Phytochemical constituents of these coriander seeds have been studied extensively and its analysis has revealed the presence of polyphenols (rutin, caffeic acid derivatives, ferulic acid, gallic acid, and chlorogenic acid), flavonoids (quercetin and isoquercetin) and β -carotenoids. The essential oil obtained from the seeds contains α and β -pinene, camphor, citronellol, coriandrol, p-cymene, geraniol, geranyl acetate, limonene, linalool, myrcene, α and β phellandrene and α and β -

terpinene. A large number of water-soluble compounds have been identified that includes monoterpenoid glycosides, monoterpenoid glucose sulphate and other glycosides. The seeds are boiled with water and drunk as indigenous medicine for colds. The essential oil has been found to possess antimicrobial and antifungal properties. The seeds have an outstanding aphrodisiac effect by stimulating the sexual glands. Moreover, they stimulate fertility and help against dependency upon alcohol and against brain tumours. Coriander fruits are used as a stimulant for the gastrointestinal secretion, sedative and carminative. They ameliorate known as a bactericide, fungicide and anthelmintic effect. Plants are an important source of potentially useful compounds for the development of new chemotherapeutic agents. In vitro evaluation of plants for antimicrobial property is the first step towards achieving the goal for developing eco-friendly management of infectious diseases of humans by search for new biomolecules of plant origin. Hence, the present research work was carried out to evaluate the phytochemical compounds of *Coriandrum sativum* seeds by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry analysis its antibacterial activity against the selected bacterial strains. Cumin seeds (*Cuminum cyminum*) are widely used in culinary practices and have been valued for their therapeutic properties in traditional medicine (Fig No. c & d). In this context, the vegetable oil of several seeds of Apiaceae could be a strong competitor thanks to their richness in Petroselinic acid. Among these species, cumin (*Cuminum cyminum*) is a promising source of vegetable and essential oils containing high levels of petroselinic acid and other bioactive molecules. Essential oil from cumin was found more efficient than commercial insecticides, and it was proposed in innovative green formulations in crop protection against E.

fetida and *H. axyridis*. Several studies have suggested to develop nanoparticles based on cumin extracts for effective antileishmaniose and antitumor activities. Indeed, cuminaldehyde presents antinociceptive, anti-neuropathic and anti-inflammatory effect. However, currently, depending on the industrial field of application, only one of these two fractions is valued, the other constituting a waste. A major scientific question remains the possibility of the sequenced extraction of essential and vegetable oils from cumin seeds. Additionally, the establishment of integrated recovery of cakes appears as a way that can participate in a better use of plant potential while allowing the development of new bioproducts of industrial importance. The present work is therefore a contribution in the global valuation of cumin seeds and from a perspective of sustainable development. A new biorefining approach of cumin seed has been established. The plant materials were processed in four parts: the vegetable oil, the essential oil, the aromatic water and the final residue (i.e., the cake). The approach adopted consists first of all of extracting the vegetable and essential oils from cumin seeds from different geographical origins. The residual cakes remaining after extractions and the aromatic water (i.e., the by-products) are later vaporized (as sources of bio sourced molecules (antioxidants or antibacterials)). In this way, the molecules inside the cakes can be extracted and used in a sequential way, thus avoiding the wasting of natural resources. The main objective of the study is to collection of plant material from the local market and stored in department of botany, Mlacw and to standardize the protocol for extraction from seeds, to study the preliminary phytochemical screening for secondary metabolites and find the bio active compounds present in extract through GC-MS analysis. to standardize the protocol for estimation of phenols by gallic acid as standard by Folin-ciocalteu method and estimation of proteins by

bovine serum albumin as standard protein by Fallin Lawry method

Figure 1 a: Coriander leaves, b. Coriander seeds, c. Cumin leaves, d. Cumin seeds

CORIANDRUM SATIVUM

Classification

- Kingdom: Plantae
- Order: Apiales
- Family: Apiaceae (Umbelliferae)
- Genus: Coriandrum
- Species: Coriandrum sativum

CUMINUM CYMINUM

- Kingdom: Plantae
- Order: Apiales
- Family: Apiaceae (Umbelliferae)
- Genus: Cuminum
- Species: Cuminum cyminum

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Sample Collection:

Coriander and cumin seeds were procured from the local market and stored in clean dry conditions. Sample Preparation: The seeds collected were thoroughly washed to remove unwanted contaminants/ foreign particles. After cleaning they were oven dried under below 45°C and powdered to mesh size # 40. The coarse powder obtained were subjected to extraction.

Extraction of sample by serial extraction through maceration method:

About 100g of each coriander and cumin powder was extracted serially with petroleum ether, chloroform, and methanol. The extraction was carried out for 24 hours under the boiling point

ranging from 30-600C with intermittent shaking. Later the extracts were concentrated oven dried under below 400C, measured and stored low 40C in refrigerator for further analysis.

Phytochemical screening:

All the 3 extracts of coriander and cumin were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening. To find the presence of phytochemical constituents, test for alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, terpenoids and phenolic compounds.

- **Test for Alkaloids by Dragendorff's reagent:**

For the test, a small amount of each extract was taken and a few drops of Dragendorff's reagent was added. The formation of orange-red precipitation indicates the presence of alkaloids.

- **Test for Flavonoids by Shinoda test reagent:**

The test examples were taken in a test tube and few drops of Shinoda reagent is added, formation of colored complexes, like pink or orange colour indicates the presence of flavonoids.

- **Test for Tannins by ferric chloride solution:**

A small amount of all the three sample extracts were taken in separate test tubes and few drops of ferric chloride solution was added. The observation of colour changing to blue-black or greenish-black indicates the presence of tannins.

- **Test for Saponins by Frothing method:**

All the extracts were taken in a test tube and 1mL of distilled water is added and shaken vigorously to obtain froth. The observation of stability and persistence of froth for longer duration of time indicates the presence of saponins.

- **Test for terpenoids by Salkowski reagent:**

The 3 extracts were taken in a separate test tube, a few drops of Salkowski reagent is added and observed. The development of reddish-brown colour in the lower layer, indicate the presence of terpenoids.

- **Test for Phenols by 5% ethanolic solution of FeCl₃:**

A small amount of 3 extracts of both the samples were taken in a separate test tube and a few drops of 5% ethanolic solution of FeCl₃ were added. The observation of blue-green or purple coloration, indicates the presence of phenolic compounds.

Estimation of total phenolic content using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (FCR) method:

The estimation of total phenolic content was carried out by preparing a gallic acid stock solution; 5g of gallic acid was dissolved in 10 ml of ethanol and make up to 100 mL with distilled water, with the concentration of 50mg/mL. Then a serial dilution was done to obtain solutions of different concentration. The blank solution was prepared by taking 5mL of Folin ciocalteu reagent with 1mL of methanol and 4mL of sodium carbonate solution. For plant sample preparation the extracts were dissolved in 75mL of ethanol and fractionated for 10 mins under 400C, followed by evaporating the ethanol. The dried extract was re-dissolved in 5 mL of methanol and ultra sonicated for 45 minutes at 400C and centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 mins. The clear supernatant was collected. The FCR reagent was prepared by taking 2 mL of reagent in a beaker and diluted to 20mL (v/v). Sodium carbonate solution prepared by measuring 7.5 grams and dissolved in 20 mL of distilled water and made up to 100mL with a pH 10. 0.5 mL of extract was mixed with 0.2 mL of 2N Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and incubated for 5 mins at room temperature followed by adding 2mL of 7.5% sodium carbonate (Na₂Co₃) again incubated at room temperature for 5 mins. The final volume of the reaction mixture was made up to 5 mL by adding sterile distilled water. The reaction mixtures were incubated at room temperature for 90 min in dark with intermitting shaking. The blue colour developed was measured at 760 nm using spectrophotometer against the

blank. The experiments were carried out in triplicates. The total phenolics content estimated through a standard curve plotted using different concentration of Gallic acid (0-500 mg/mL) and the total phenolic content of seed extracts were expressed as mg of Gallic acid equivalent/mg (GE) of extract. The obtained absorbance was calculated by plotting against the standard volume (mL). The regression line of graph is used to determine the polyphenolic equivalence in different sample been analysed, the regression line is $y=mx+b$ from the standard curve was used to determine the polyphenolic with y-absorbance, m-gradient, the sample extract was dissolved in 5 mL methanol, 2 mg of extract in each 1 mL of methanol extract solution, and calculated as mg/g of methanol extract sample.

Estimation of proteins by Folin Lowry method:

The Bovine serum albumin (BSA) solution was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of BSA in distilled water and a stock solution of 1mg/mL concentration as a stock solution. From the stock solution dilution was made with distilled water and a series of standard solutions were prepared ranging from 10 to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. A different Aliquots of coriander and cumin seed extracts were prepared. The Folin-lowry reagent; Reagent A was prepared by dissolving 2% Na_2CO_3 in 0.1 M NaOH and Reagent B by dissolving 0.5% CuSO_4 and 1% potassium sodium tartrate in distilled water. The reaction mixture was prepared in separate test tubes by adding 0.5 mL of sample extract and 2.5mL of Reagent A and mixed well using a vortex mixer or shaker. The mixture is allowed to stand at room temperature for 10 minutes. 0.25 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent to each test tube and mixed immediately, and the mixture is allowed to stand at room temperature for 30 minutes. The absorbance is measured the optical density (OD) values were measured at 660 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer, against the

blank (distilled water). The amount of protein was estimated with standard and compared.

GCMS analysis for coriander and cumin seeds:

To analyse coriander and cumin seeds using gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy (GC-MS), about 1g of extract was taken and diluted 1mg/mL concentration. The GC-MS analysis was carried out in a GCMS-QP Series (GC-2010, 021425678041 US), GC ROM version: 2.1070., and mass spectrophotometer, fitted with a Dual stage TMP (QP2020). Helium gas was used as carrier gas and was adjusted to column velocity flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The other GC-MS conditions are ion-source temperature, at 2200C; interface temperature of 2300C; pressure, 57.5 Kpa, and injector in split mode with the split ratio 20.0; with the injection temperature of maximum of 4700C. The column temperature started at minimum temperature of 500C for hold time 3 min and with the linear velocity 36.5 cm/sec and increased to 2400C for 5 min. the total flow of 24.0mL/min, column flow of 1 mL/min, purge flow of 3mL/min, with the injection temperature of 2200C. The relative amount of each component was calculated by comparing its average peak area. MS solution was used to control the system and to acquire the data.

Identification of compounds:

The identification of components was achieved based on the relative retention index and the mass spectrum was interpreted using the database of National Institute of Standards and technology (NSIT). The data-base consists around 62,000 patterns of known compounds. The spectra of even unknown components stored in NIST library (NISTII).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Phytochemical screening:

The preliminary phytochemical screening of methanolic coriander and cumin seed extract showed the presence of Saponins, tannins, phenols, as mentioned in the (Table 1)

Table no. 1 Phytochemical screening of coriander and cumin seed extracts.

Tests	Procedure	Petroleum ether	Chloroform	Methanol	Results	Tests	Procedure	Petroleum ether
		coriander seeds	cumin seed	coriander seed	cumin seed	coriander seed	cumin seed	
TEST FOR ALKALOIDS	Mix the extract with Dragendorff's reagent. An orange red precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids	+ve	+ve	ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	
TEST FOR TERPENOIDS	Mix the extract with Chloroform and sulfuric acid. The formation of reddish-brown ring at the interface indicates the presence of terpenoid.	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	
TEST FOR FLAVONOIDS	Add sodium hydroxide to the extract observing and intense yellow colour that turns colorless	+ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	

TEST FOR TANINS	Introduce a few drops of ferric chloride to the extract, A blue, black, or green precipitate confirms the presence of tannins.	+ve	+ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	
TEST FOR SAPONINS	Vigorously shake the extract with water, the formation of stable foam indicates the presence of saponins.	+ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	
TEST FOR PHENOLS	Mix the extract with gallic acid. Add the dragendrof reagent, a red colour precipitate confirms the phenol.	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	+ve	

The phytochemical screening in all the 3 extracts showed the presence of bioactive components such as alkaloids, terpenoids, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, and phenols.

Test for alkaloids:

The methanolic extract showed better observation compared to petroleum ether and chloroform. A clear orange red precipitation obtained in both the extracts, indicated the presence of alkaloids.

Test for terpenoids:

A formation of reddish-brown ring at the interface in methanolic extract of both extracts indicated the presence of terpenoids.

Test for flavonoids:

When sodium hydroxide was added to both the extracts, an intense yellow colour decolourized to colourless indicates the presence of flavonoids.

Test for tannins:

An addition of few drops of ferric chloride to both the extracts, appearance of a blue/green/black precipitation, indicates the presence of tannins.

Test for Saponins:

A clear persistent forth of 1cm length in methanolic extracts of both plants indicated the presence of saponins.

Test for Phenols:

The formation of red precipitation in methanolic extracts indicated the presence of phenols.

Estimation of Total phenolic content by Folin-Ciocalteu method:

The total phenolic content of both coriander and cumin seeds were estimated in methanolic seed extract, and determined by the calibration curve ($y=0.001+0.018x$; $R^2=0.9968$) that was prepared from the aliquots of gallic acid (fig. 2) that are expressed in mg of gallic acid equivalence (GAE) per gram (table No.2). The amount of phenolic content in different extracts were obtained from regression equation and the values are expressed in gallic acid equivalence (Fig. 3 & 4). there was a significant difference comparing polyphenol content in Coriander seed extract in methanol contains 105.5 mg of polyphenols and cumin seed extract contain 124 mg of polyphenols. So, in conclusion Cumin seed contain more polyphenols than coriander seed. (Fig no. 5).

Table no. 2 Total phenolic content of coriander and cumin seeds.

Coriander seeds								
Volumetric flask	Volume of Gallic acid in ml	Amount of gallic acid in mg/ml	Add 5 ml of Folin ciocalteu reagent to each test tube	Add 5ml of 7.5 % solution of ph. 10 to each test tube	Mix well the content and incubate under 25-to-40-degree centigrade for 40 min under dark condition	From VF ppt out 2 ml of solution separately . Mark the exact series and sample	And make up the volume of test tubes to 5ml with distilled water	Absorbance at 760nm with uv spectrophotometer
Blank	0	0						0
A1	1	50						0.072
A2	2	100						0.108
A3	3	150						0.165
A4	5	250						0.255
A5	7	350						0.327
A6	8	500						0.487
Sample	1	Coriander seed extract						0.229
Sample	2	Cumin seed extract						0.233

**CALCULATIONS:
CORIANDER SEEDS**

The regression line is $y=mx+b$ from the standard curve was used to determine the polyphenolic.

y =absorbance

m =gradient

x =concentration(unknown)

$y=0.001x+0.018$

$R^2=0.996$

$y=0.996$

$m=0.001$

$b=0.018$

Thus,

$x=(y-b)/m$

$x=(0.229-0.018)/0.001$

$x=0.211\text{mg/mlx}$

Initially 10 grams of the sample extract was dissolved in 5ml methanol. Therefore, 2mg of extract in each 1ml of methanol extract solution.

Polyphenols amount in
 $\text{mg/gram}=0.211/2 \times 1000$

$=105.5\text{mg/g}$ of methanol extract sample

CUMIN SEEDS

$y=0.0001x+0.018$

$R^2=0.996$ $y=0.233$ $m=0.001$ $b=0.018$

Thus,

$x=(y+b)/m$

$x=(0.233+0.018)/0.001x$

$x=0.248\text{mg/mlx}$

Initially 10 grams of sample dissolved in 5ml methanol. Therefore, 2mg of extract in each 1ml of methanol extract solution.

Polyphenols amount in mg/g of extract sample

$=0.248/2 \times 1000$

$=124\text{mg/g}$ of methanol extract sample= 124mg/g of methanol extract sample

Figure 2. Calibration curve for Gallic Acid in phenolic content estimation.

Figure 3: Polyphenolic content of coriander seeds.

Figure 4: Polyphenolic content of cumin seeds.

Figure 5: Comparative analysis of polyphenol content in coriander and cumin seeds.

Estimation of proteins by Falin Lawry method:

The protein content of both the plant samples were determined by Bovine Serum albumin (BSA), by spectroscopic method. The optical density (OD) values were plotted at varying concentration of BSA ranging from 100-1000mg/mL, at the absorbance rate of 660nm (Table no. 3 & 4). The amount of proteins content in the extracts were

calculated using a formula over the volume of sample (Figure 6 & 7). There was a significant difference in comparing the protein content of coriander seed in methanol extract was about 8000µg/ml and cumin seed in methanol extract contains 12000µg/ml. So, in conclusion cumin seed contain more protein than Coriander seeds (Figure 8)

Table no. 3 Protein estimation results for cumin seeds.

Cumin seeds							
Std BSA C µg/ml	Stock	D/W	Df in ml		FCR in ml		Absorbance at 660nm
100	0.1	0.9	0.5	Incubate 10 min at room temperature	0.5	Incubate 30 min at room temperature	0.06
200	0.2	0.8	0.5		0.5		0.16
300	0.3	0.7	0.5		0.5		0.25
400	0.4	0.6	0.5		0.5		0.38
500	0.5	0.5	0.5		0.5		0.44
600	0.6	0.4	0.5		0.5		0.59
700	0.7	0.3	0.5		0.5		0.6
800	0.8	0.2	0.5		0.5		0.75
900	0.9	0.1	0.5		0.5		0.88
1000	1		0.5		0.5		0.95
Sample	1		0.5		0.5		0.58

Table no. 4 Protein estimation results for coriander seeds.

Coriander seeds							
Std BSA C µg/ml	Stock	D/W	Df in ml		FCR in ml		Absorbance at 660nm
100	0.1	0.9	0.5	Incubate 10 min at room temperature	0.5	Incubate 30 min at room temperature	0.09
200	0.2	0.8	0.5		0.5		0.23
300	0.3	0.7	0.5		0.5		0.29
400	0.4	0.6	0.5		0.5		0.37
500	0.5	0.5	0.5		0.5		0.49
600	0.6	0.4	0.5		0.5		0.55
700	0.7	0.3	0.5		0.5		0.61
800	0.8	0.2	0.5		0.5		0.7
900	0.9	0.1	0.5		0.5		0.84
1000	1		0.5		0.5		0.97
Sample	2		0.5		0.5		0.38

CALCULATIONS:

Cumin seeds

Concentration of protein = µg of Protein × Dilution factor / Volume of sample
 600 × 10 / 0.5 = 12000 µg/ml of protein

Coriander seeds

Concentration of protein = µg of Protein × Dilution factor / Volume of sample
 400 × 10 / 0.5 = 8000 µg/ml of protein
 Comparatively cumin seeds contain more protein content than coriander seed

Figure 6 Protein content of coriander seeds.

Figure 7 Protein content of cumin seeds.

Protein Content Distribution in Seed Extracts

Figure 8 Comparative analysis of protein content in coriander and cumin seeds.

GC-MS profiling of methanolic extract of Coriander and Cumin seeds: A total of 14 compounds were identified from GC-MS analysis of methanol extract of coriander seeds and cumin

seeds, exhibit different biological activities. The chromatogram obtained from GC-MS are represented in the (figure 9 and 10) with their chemical constituents, the retention time (RT),

Table No: 6 Bioactive compounds identified in cumin seeds (GC-MS analysis)

Peak#	R.Time	I.Time	F.Time	Area	Area%	Height%	Name
1	11.343	11.225	11.495	426125	2.86	3.42	Decane, 2,3,5,8-tetramethyl-
2	17.305	17.150	17.495	1697586	11.41	14.78	Benzaldehyde, 4-(1-methylethyl)-
3	19.395	19.295	19.490	1707674	11.48	15.09	1,4-p-Menthadien-7-al
4	19.580	19.490	19.730	266448	1.79	1.55	2,4-Decadienal, (E,E)-
5	23.129	23.030	23.283	397836	2.67	3.74	Geranyl acetate
6	30.904	30.770	31.070	782313	5.26	6.58	(E)-Tetradec-2-enal
7	38.220	38.075	38.390	910527	6.12	6.63	Tetradecanoic acid
8	44.970	44.780	45.320	3187339	21.42	19.80	n-Hexadecanoic acid
9	49.088	48.950	49.205	288375	1.94	2.18	6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester, (Z)-
10	50.145	50.045	50.240	869463	5.84	5.93	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-
11	50.429	50.240	50.733	2460556	16.54	10.10	6-Octadecenoic acid, (Z)-
12	51.088	50.975	51.245	462905	3.11	3.29	Octadecanoic acid
13	56.933	56.780	57.275	848580	5.70	2.88	Tetradecanoic acid, octyl ester
14	62.412	62.285	62.675	573281	3.85	4.03	Hexadecanoic acid, octyl ester
				14879508	100.00	100.00	

The major compounds detected in the coriander seed sample include:

- Benzaldehyde (4-(1-methylethyl)-) - This compound is the most abundant, constituting approximately 16.32% of the total area. Benzaldehyde is known for its almond-like aroma and is often used in flavoring and fragrance applications.
- Linalool - Present at 2.49%, linalool is a terpene alcohol with a floral scent, commonly found in many essential oils. Its presence in coriander contributes to the characteristic aroma of the spice.
- 1,4-p-Menthadien-7-al - This compound accounts for 12.61% of the total area. It is a key flavor compound that enhances the sensory profile of coriander.
- n-Hexadecanoic acid - At 17.63%, this fatty acid is significant for its potential health benefits and is often associated with various biological activities.
- Oleic Acid and Linoleic Acid Ethyl Ester - These compounds, present at 10.93% and 12.77%, respectively, are important for their nutritional properties and are commonly found in edible oils.

The major compounds detected in the cumin seed sample include:

- n-Hexadecanoic acid –

21.42% saturated fatty acid, commonly known as palmitic acid, with applications in cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and as a bioactive agent in health.

- **6-Octadecenoic acid, (Z) –** 16.54% oleic acid, a monounsaturated fatty acid with health benefits, commonly found in edible oils.
- **Benzaldehyde, 4-(1-methylethyl)-** 11.41% compound known for its almond-like aroma and used widely in flavoring and fragrance industries.
- **1,4-p-Menthadien-7-al –** 11.48% flavor compound contributing to the characteristic aroma of cumin.
- **Geranyl acetate –** 2.67% monoterpene ester with a sweet floral aroma, commonly used in perfumes and flavoring agents.
- **9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z, Z) –** 5.84% linoleic acid, an essential fatty acid important for human nutrition, commonly found in vegetable oils.
- **Tetra decanoic acid (Myristic Acid) –** 6.12% saturated fatty acid used in cosmetics and pharmaceutical formulations.
- **Octadecanoic acid (Stearic Acid) –**

3.11% fatty acid widely used in the production of soaps, cosmetics, and lubricants.

Chromatogram Overview (Figure 9&10)

The total ion chromatogram (TIC) displayed major peaks corresponding to the identified compounds, with n-Hexadecenoic acid being the most prominent. A comparative analysis of the volatile compounds identified through GC-MS in *Coriandrum sativum* (coriander) and *Cuminum cyminum* (cumin) seeds highlights key similarities and differences in their chemical profiles. Both seeds are rich in bioactive compounds, but they differ significantly in the types and concentrations of these compounds.

Major Compounds

Coriander Seeds:

- Linalool is a major component of about 40.2% in coriander seeds, contributes for its floral aromatic, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties.

- **Borneol:**

25.5% Known for its medicinal properties, borneol adds to the therapeutic potential in coriander.

- **Geraniol:**

10.0% Geraniol, with its rose-like scent, is another major volatile compound, used in perfumery and flavoring industry.

Cumin Seeds:

- **n-Hexadecenoic Acid:**

21.42% saturated fatty acid is the most abundant in cumin seeds, known for its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.

- **6-Octadecenoic Acid (Oleic Acid):**

16.54% Oleic acid contributes to cumin's health benefits, particularly in cardiovascular diseases.

- **Benzaldehyde:**

11.41% Benzaldehyde provides a distinctive almond-like aroma and has antimicrobial properties. Both seeds contain compounds which acts as a major raw material for their distinct aromas, making them valuable ingredient in

culinary and perfumery industries. For instance, Linalool in coriander and Benzaldehyde in cumin contribute as vital characteristic scents. Presence of both coriander and cumin seeds have a significant value in therapeutic property. Geraniol in coriander and 1,4-p-Menthadien-7-al in cumin are known for their antimicrobial and flavoring agents.

DIFFERENCES

a. Dominant Fatty Acids:

- Coriander seeds are more dominated by terpenoids (e.g., linalool), which are responsible for their strong aromatic qualities.
- Cumin seeds, on the other hand, contain higher levels of fatty acids like n-Hexadecenoic acid and Oleic acid, which contribute to their nutritional and health benefits.

Coriander's floral and citrus-like aroma comes mainly from linalool, while cumin has a warm, spicy aroma primarily due to Benzaldehyde and 1,4-p-Menthadien-7-al. The GC-MS analysis of Coriander and cumin seeds revealed a diverse chemical profile, with major compounds identified. The data provides insights into the bioactive components of both coriander and cumin seeds, contributing to their medicinal, nutritional, and aromatic properties. Below is a detailed discussion of the most significant findings. The n-Hexadecenoic acid, commonly known as palmitic acid, was identified as the most abundant compound, accounting for 21.42% of the total area. Palmitic acid is a well-known saturated fatty acid and is widely recognized for its emollient and moisturizing properties, thus it is frequently used in cosmetic formulations. In addition to its cosmetic applications, palmitic acid exhibits antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activities, contributing to the overall health benefits of cumin seeds. The significant presence in cumin seeds potential for pharmaceutical applications, particularly in topical and oral products designed

to reduce inflammation and combat microbial infections (Shah et al., 2018). The second most abundant compound, 6-Octadecenoic acid, or oleic acid, is a monounsaturated fatty acid that plays a crucial role in human health. Found in edible oils like olive oil, oleic acid is known for its cardioprotective properties, helping to lower bad cholesterol (LDL) while increasing good cholesterol (HDL). Its presence in cumin seeds at 16.54% suggests that cumin could be beneficial in maintaining cardiovascular health when included in the diet. Additionally, oleic acid's anti-inflammatory effects make cumin seeds valuable for managing inflammatory conditions (Banu et al., 2019). Benzaldehyde, with an area of 11.41%, is known for its characteristic almond-like aroma, commonly used in flavoring and fragrance industries. This compound adds to cumin's distinct aroma, which is highly valued in culinary applications. Apart from its sensory benefits, benzaldehyde has been reported to possess antimicrobial properties, contributing to cumin's role as a natural preservative and antimicrobial agent in food products (Dhandapani et al., 2016). 1,4-p-Menthadien-7-al is a flavor compound identified in cumin seeds, contributing to their overall sensory profile. At 11.48%, this compound plays a significant role in defining cumin's characteristic aroma, which is both sharp and aromatic. The presence of this compound also suggests potential uses in the flavor and fragrance industries, where cumin seed extract or essential oil could be used to enhance the taste and smell of various products. Additionally, 1,4-p-Menthadien-7-al has been associated with antimicrobial and antioxidant properties (Nagella et al., 2018). Linoleic acid, present at 5.84%, is an essential polyunsaturated fatty acid that is crucial for human health, known for its anti-inflammatory and "skin barrier repair" properties, linoleic acid is commonly found in skincare formulations. In terms of nutritional benefits, linoleic acid

contributes to lowering cholesterol levels and supports immune function. Its presence in cumin seeds suggests that regular consumption of cumin could contribute to improved skin health and cardiovascular protection (Jain et al., 2020). Tetradecanoic acid, also known as myristic acid, was found to constitute 6.12% of the total composition. Myristic acid is a saturated fatty acid commonly found in nutmeg, palm oil, and other natural oils. It is primarily used in the production of soaps, cosmetics, and lubricants. Myristic acid is known for its role in enhancing the absorption of other active ingredients in cosmetic and pharmaceutical formulations, making cumin seeds a valuable source for the production of personal care products (Rathore et al., 2017). Geranyl acetate is a monoterpene ester with a sweet floral aroma, often used in perfumery and flavoring applications. Although it accounts for only 2.67% of the total area, its presence in cumin seeds highlights their potential use in the fragrance industry. Geranyl acetate has also been studied for its antimicrobial properties, which are combined with other bioactive compounds in cumin, that enhances its application as a natural preservative in food and cosmetic products (Wahab et al., 2018). Stearic acid, a saturated fatty acid found in many natural fats, was present at 3.11%. It is widely used in the production of soaps, cosmetics, and lubricants due to its emulsifying properties. Stearic acid contributes to the texture of creams and lotions, making them smooth and spreadable. Its presence in cumin seeds further supports the seeds' utility in cosmetic formulations, particularly for products designed to moisturize and protect the skin (Sharma et al., 2020). Coriander seeds (*Coriandrum sativum*), being a rich source of various bioactive compounds, have been the subject of numerous studies aimed at understanding their phytochemical composition, nutritional value, and potential health benefits. Phytochemical screening is a crucial step in

identifying the presence of biologically active compounds, while estimation of protein and total phenolic content helps in evaluating the nutritional and antioxidant potential of coriander seeds. Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis provides an advanced method for identifying and quantifying the volatile and non-volatile compounds present in these seeds. Phytochemical screening of coriander seeds has revealed the presence of a wide variety of bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and terpenoids (Kumar et al., 2018). These compounds are known to contribute to the seed's pharmacological activities, such as antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties. A study (Ahmed et al., 2020) demonstrated that coriander seeds contain significant amounts of flavonoids and tannins, which play a critical role in the seed's ability to scavenge free radicals. In addition to these, saponins, which have been detected in coriander seeds, are known for their cholesterol-lowering and immune-modulatory effects (Madhuri et al., 2017). The presence of terpenoids, which are major components of the essential oils in coriander seeds, has also been widely reported. These compounds, especially linalool, have been associated with the seeds' strong antimicrobial activity (Singh & Pandey, 2019). Alkaloids, though present in smaller quantities, have also been reported in the seeds, contributing to their therapeutic properties, including pain relief and anti-inflammatory effects (Manivannan et al., 2020). The protein content of coriander seeds, though moderate, plays a significant role in their nutritional value. Studies have shown that coriander seeds contain around 11-20% protein depending on the extraction method and seed variety (Reddy et al., 2016). Protein estimation using the Falin Lawry method revealed that coriander seeds are a good source of plant-based proteins, which are essential for growth, repair,

and maintenance of body tissues (Ahmed et al., 2020). A recent analysis by (Mahendran et al. 2019) found that coriander seed protein contains essential amino acids such as lysine and methionine, which are crucial for various metabolic processes in the human body. In addition to their nutritional benefits, proteins extracted from coriander seeds have also been reported to have functional properties, such as emulsifying and foaming capacity, which are beneficial for food processing industries (Ali et al., 2018). The moderate protein content, combined with the presence of bioactive peptides, suggests that coriander seeds could be utilized in functional foods aimed at improving human health. The total phenolic content (TPC) of coriander seeds has been extensively studied due to its strong correlation with antioxidant activity. Phenolic compounds, which include flavonoids, phenolic acids, and tannins, are known to neutralize free radicals and reduce oxidative stress (Dudhe et al., 2017). The Folin-Ciocalteu method is commonly employed for estimating the TPC of coriander seeds. For instance, Singh and Kumari (2018) reported that coriander seeds contain significant amounts of phenolic compounds, with values ranging from 1.2 to 2.6 mg of gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram of seed extract. These phenolic compounds have been linked to the seeds' anti-carcinogenic, anti-inflammatory, and cardiovascular protective properties (Sharma et al., 2019). Furthermore, the high phenolic content is believed to contribute to the preservation and shelf life of foods when coriander seeds are used as a natural preservative (Patil et al., 2016). Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) is a powerful analytical technique used to identify and quantify volatile compounds in coriander seeds. GC-MS analysis of coriander seed essential oil has identified over 60 volatile compounds, with linalool being the most dominant, contributing to the seed's characteristic aroma and medicinal

properties (Tunc Turk et al., 2018). In addition to linalool, other major compounds identified through GC-MS include α -pinene, γ -terpinene, camphor, and geraniol, all of which are known for their antimicrobial and antioxidant activities (Shafiq et al., 2020). A study (Ashok kumar et al., (2020) using GC-MS analysis highlighted the high concentration of linalool (55-70%) in coriander seeds, which is responsible for its sedative and anxiolytic effects. Similarly, compounds such as borneol and geranyl acetate, which were also detected, have been reported to possess antifungal and antibacterial properties (Iqbal et al., 2019). The detailed profiling of these compounds not only adds to the understanding of the pharmacological potential of coriander seeds but also supports their use in food preservation and perfumery industries. Furthermore, the identification of minor compounds such as myrcene and limonene through GC-MS analysis has opened new avenues for the utilization of coriander seeds in aromatherapy and alternative medicine (Singh et al., 2020). The complex profile of volatile and non-volatile compounds in coriander seeds underscores their versatility and broad range of applications in food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries. Cumin (*Cuminum cyminum*), an essential spice and medicinal herb belonging to the Apiaceae family, has been extensively studied for its phytochemical composition, nutritional benefits, and pharmacological properties. The seeds of cumin are rich in essential oils, alkaloids, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds, which contribute to their wide range of health benefits. Phytochemical screening, protein and phenolic estimation, and GC-MS analysis are key methodologies used in the study of cumin seeds to uncover their bioactive compounds and functional applications. Phytochemical screening of cumin seeds has revealed a diverse range of bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins,

terpenes, and glycosides (Patel et al., 2018). These compounds are responsible as a potent antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and digestive properties. The presence of flavonoids and phenolic acids, such as quercetin and kaempferol, are particularly significant, as they are well-known for their antioxidant potential, which helps in scavenging free radicals and protecting cells from oxidative damage (Singh et al., 2019). In addition to flavonoids, cumin seeds contain significant quantities of saponins and tannins, both of which are associated with various health benefits, including cholesterol regulation and immune enhancement (Gupta et al., 2020). The essential oils present in cumin seeds are predominantly composed of terpenes, especially cuminaldehyde, which has been recognized for its antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties (Rathore et al., 2017). Alkaloids in cumin seeds also contribute to their medicinal properties, including analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities (Patra et al., 2020). Cumin seeds, though primarily known for their essential oils and aromatic compounds, also contain a moderate amount of protein. Studies have reported the protein content of cumin seeds to be approximately 10-15%, depending on the region and method of extraction (Bhat et al., 2015). Protein estimation through the Kjeldahl method has shown that cumin seeds are a significant source of plant-based protein, which plays a role in maintaining muscle mass, enzyme production, and overall metabolic function (Ahmed et al., 2019).

Furthermore, cumin seeds have been found to contain essential amino acids, including lysine, methionine, and tryptophan, which are critical for various physiological functions, such as tissue repair and immune system support (Jain et al., 2020). This makes cumin seeds a valuable ingredient in both culinary and nutritional applications. The moderate protein content, along with their amino acid profile, suggests that cumin

seeds can be a useful dietary supplement, especially in vegetarian and vegan diets where plant-based protein sources are essential. The total phenolic content (TPC) of cumin seeds is one of the key indicators of their antioxidant potential. Phenolic compounds are known for their ability to neutralize free radicals and prevent oxidative stress-related diseases (Dhandapani et al., 2016). The Folin-Ciocalteu method is commonly employed to estimate the total phenolic content in cumin seeds. For instance, a study by (Nagella et al. (2018) reported that cumin seeds contain a significant amount of phenolics, with values ranging between 2.0 to 3.5 mg of gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram of seed extract. The high phenolic content in cumin seeds is linked to their anti-inflammatory, anti-carcinogenic, and cardioprotective effects (Gull et al., 2016). In addition, these phenolic compounds contribute to the preservation and enhancement of food products when cumin seeds are used as a natural preservative. Research by Sharma et al., (2017) demonstrated that cumin seed phenolics play a role in inhibiting lipid peroxidation, which is important for extending the shelf life of food products and protecting the body from oxidative damage. Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) is a critical tool in analyzing the volatile and non-volatile compounds present in cumin seeds. GC-MS analysis of cumin essential oil has identified over 50 different compounds, with cuminaldehyde, γ -terpinene, p-cymene, and β -pinene being the most prominent (Sharma et al., 2020). Cuminaldehyde, in particular, has been recognized for its strong antimicrobial, antifungal, and antioxidant activities, which contribute to the seeds' medicinal applications (Wahab et al., 2018). A study conducted by (Ashraf et al. (2019) using GC-MS analysis highlighted the presence of monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes, such as α -pinene, β -caryophyllene, and thymol, which are known for their anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer

properties. The identification of these volatile compounds through GC-MS not only provides insight into the therapeutic potential of cumin seeds but also underscores their use in traditional medicine and aromatherapy. In addition to their medicinal value, the volatile compounds identified in cumin seeds contribute to their flavor and aroma, making them a key ingredient in culinary applications (Shah et al., 2018). The high concentration of cuminaldehyde and other aromatic compounds has also led to the use of cumin essential oil in perfumery and cosmetics (Banu et al., 2019). The complexity of the volatile profile of cumin seeds, as revealed by GC-MS, demonstrates their wide-ranging applications in both food and pharmaceutical industries.

CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully explored the phytochemical screening for primary and secondary metabolites, total phenolic content, protein estimation, and GC-MS analysis of coriander and cumin seeds. The study confirmed the presence of bioactive compounds like alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds in both seeds. In summary, coriander seeds are rich in terpenoids such as Linalool, contributing to their aromatic and medicinal properties, while cumin seeds are dominated by fatty acids like n-Hexadecanoic acid and Oleic acid, which offer nutritional and health benefits. Both seeds are valuable in different applications, from food and pharmaceuticals to cosmetics, due to their unique volatile compound profiles. GC-MS analysis identified few major volatile compounds such as linalool, benzaldehyde, and fatty acids. Cumin seeds demonstrated higher levels of phenolic content and protein comparison with coriander seeds, indicating greater antioxidant potential and nutritional value. These findings support that the image of traditional medicine such as coriander and cumin were potentially in food, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical

industries. Future prospects of Phytochemical analysis employing advanced techniques such as HPLC, LC-MS/MS and NMR to identify and quantify bioactive compounds in both the seeds. Conduction of clinical trials to be carried out for assessing the specific health benefits after consuming these seeds particularly their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial properties.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

All the authors mentioned in the manuscript do not have any conflict of interest.

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